

HYGROTHERMAL EFFECTS ON ADHESIVE BONDED JOINTS
IN COMPOSITE MATERIAL STRUCTURES

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The effects of combined high temperature and high humidity (termed hygrothermal effects) over prolonged periods of time have been found to be significantly deleterious to the performance of structures composed of polymer matrix composite materials. In this study, hygrothermal effects on polymer adhesive bonded joints in composite structures is investigated to assess their sensitivity to that environment.